

MANAGING NOISE IN HOMOMORPHIC CALCULATIONS

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Abstract

Homomorphic Encryption (HE) has been identified as one of the effective methods in preserving data confidentiality during the outsourced computations. Homomorphic Encryption (HE) schemes can be classified into different categories depending on the homomorphism properties and the type of operations that are being done through these methods. However, some of the homomorphic encryption schemes introduce noise in their calculations which guarantee the security of the cryptosystems. In such schemes, the amount of noise continues to increase by the computation operations applied to the encrypted data. This bounded element could be a small integer, or a small polynomial based on the type of the scheme. Although the noise is a small element, the homomorphic operations increase its size until it becomes influential at some point. Thus, this problem leads to damage the content of the encrypted message as well as losing data. Even some homomorphic encryption schemes use different noise management techniques to control the noise size, but they consume an extra time and effort from both the data owner (client) and a server. All noise management techniques definitely require decrypting the data first before applying any of them on the message after every new operation. Thus, homomorphic encryption schemes that use noise are impractical. Furthermore, there is currently no noise managing mechanism at the server side that can verify if the noise had exceeded the given limit or not. Our proposed method is responsible to

manage the level of noise in the homomorphically encrypted data in the cloud service provider. The proposed method also verifies the homomorphic encryption calculation such that the calculation will not be corrupted by the noise generated by the homomorphic encryption schemes.

1 INTRODUCTION

The demanding needs of modern computing have prompted many enterprises scrambling to outsource their data solution to Cloud Service Provider (CSP). CSP is defined as an environment in which users can share their resources in pay per use model. The resources are stored centrally and accessible from anywhere. Providing a secure and efficient platform in CSP is one of the prime concerns in the current era. CSP provides 3 main services named, IaaS (Infrastructure-as-a-Service), PaaS (Platform-as-a-Service), and SaaS (Software-as-a-Service), to raise performance efficiency, easy maintenance, provisioning of resources and cost-saving to the adopters [1]. These services allow enterprises to conveniently store, maintain, manage, and back up data files remotely from different geographic locations [2]. The cloud market is brimming with Amazon Web Services (AWS), Microsoft Azure, IBM cloud, and many more pioneering and established CSP, which are building competitive products with innovations. The number of enterprises depending on cloud appropriation has practically multiplied over the most recent couple of years and was expected

that 83% of enterprise workloads would be in the cloud [3].

The current success of cloud services is mostly on cloud storage providers where Google Drive, DropBox, and iCloud, are the most famous examples of cloud storage [4]. However, the cloud computing is gaining ground in the digital world nowadays because it ensures better collaboration, efficiency, transparency, and innovation in its solutions [5]. However, securely outsource computing is a challenge. One possible solution is to harness the possibility of doing the calculation in encrypted form as provided by homomorphic encryption.

Data sovereignty is lost once the data is stored in a remote CSP. This absence of control for data security presents data confidentiality and integrity protection problems. To address such issue, homomorphic encryption as proposed by Rivest [6], can be used to enable private cloud storage and computation solutions in CSP. Homomorphism encryption (HE), unlike traditional encryption methods, can preserve data confidentiality during computing, processing, and storage [7].

HE allows corresponding third parties to compute complex mathematical operations over encrypted data without having to decipher them, which makes secure computation delegation to third-party possible. HE schemes are malleable in design which can perform multiplication or/and addition property. Depending on the supported homomorphism features, HE schemes can be classified into three categories, namely Partial Homomorphic Encryption (PHE), Somewhat Homomorphic Encryption (SWHE), and Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) [8].

PHE schemes can perform one type of computation operation on the encrypted data at a time. It could be either an additive homomorphism that supports only addition operations (such as Pai scheme) [9] or

multiplicative homomorphism that supports just multiplication operations (such as RSA scheme) [6].

An SWHE scheme has some homomorphic properties only. It has the ability to perform both additive and multiplicative homomorphism, however, with a limited number of operations. This limitation comes from the compensation of increasing noise parameter in the generated homomorphic ciphertext. In general, each homomorphic encryption scheme outputs a ciphertext with a noise parameter, and the decryption works properly as long as the noise is less than the inherited security parameters. The cryptosystem's faintness is controlling the amount of noise parameter to correctly decrypt resultant ciphertexts of homomorphic operations [10].

On the other hand, an FHE is similar to SWHE except that there are different noise management techniques that have been used to prevent the increment in accumulated noise during computation. Bootstrapping, modulus switching, scale invariant, and flattening are different noise management techniques to control the growth of the noise and make the number of operations unlimited. Thus, FHE schemes can apply unlimited chaining of algebraic operations such as (Gentry) [11]. FHE schemes are not practically efficient yet while PHE schemes are currently in use in a limited number of applications [12]–[15].

Both SWHE and FHE add the noise parameter which is a limited element of randomness into the ciphertext while encrypting. This element is defined by the type of the homomorphic encryption scheme where the limit varies for each set of parameters that are used. The purpose of using the noise is to improve the security of the cryptosystems, in which it is easy for the trusted parties who hold some extra information to remove and disclose the original message but concealing the message from

adversaries who do not have the unknown extra information [16].

However, the disadvantage of using the noise is that the noise will grow after some time to pose a danger to the original data. Therefore, the scheme will corrupt the message and make it impossible to recover [17]. Thus, the number of computational operations are limited because the error probability of decryption function is imposed by the noise [16]. Figure 1 shows the effect of noise size on the message after operations. Even though the FHE scheme uses techniques to manage the noise, but they are not practical due to the extra time and effort they take to adjust the noise parameter after each operation [10].

Figure 1: The effect of noise after operations.

2 PROPOSED WORK

To manage the level of the noise in homomorphically encrypted data on the CSP domain we propose to use the Residue Number System (RNS). Encrypted data can be combined

with the arithmetic coding known as Residue Eight (RE). RE method can also verify the HE calculation such that the calculation will not be corrupted by the noise generated by the HE schemes. We describe a new method of cryptanalysis based on a property of RNS and theory of numbers.

Our data block consists of two sets; the actual data part and the RE part as Most Significant Bit (MSB) then the data owner (client) encrypts the block and sends it to the CSP. CSP stores the encrypted data and does the required operations. In order to control noise size as well as verify the calculations requested after each operation CSP does a list of comparison operations between MSB of the message and RE value. The data will be stored in the cloud unless the value of comparison operations is false. False data is returned to the client to identify the cause and make the decision based on it.

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